

HISTORY OF CONTINUED FRACTIONS

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Abstract:

Continued fraction is most significant field in mathematics. It is commonly used to approximate real numbers and solve Diophantine equations. In this paper we have presented an over view of continued fractions and its quick history.

1. Introduction:

Continued fraction has arises from the ancient period. Few ancient mathematicians have used continued fraction in their work without giving any specific name or definition for continued fraction. In 17th centuries, the theory of continued fraction has begun to bloom as a field in number theory and started to grow progressively. Presently, continued fraction became one of the trending field in number theory due to its applications.

1.1 Sketch of Continued Fractions:

Continued fraction, the name itself explains its meaning that is, it is an expression of the form,

$$a_0 + \frac{b_1}{a_1 + \frac{b_2}{a_2 + \frac{b_3}{\ddots}}} \quad (1)$$

Where $a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots$ can be any real or complex numbers and the number of terms may be finite or infinite.

The following expression is called the simple continued fraction which is more popular.

$$a_0 + \frac{1}{a_1 + \frac{1}{a_2 + \frac{1}{\ddots}}} \quad (2)$$

Where a_0 is any integer and $a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots$ are all positive integer.

1.2 Notations:

Here we have mentioned a few notations for continued fraction which was given by some mathematicians in their works.

First formal notation of (1) is introduced by Pietro Antonio Cataldi in 1613 as follows,

$$a_0 \& \frac{b_1}{a_1} \& \frac{b_2}{a_2} \& \dots$$

Where '&' represents '+' and '.' represents where the following fractions to be added.

German mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss proposed the notation for (1) as mentioned below in 1813 in terms of K , "Kettenbruch" means "Continued Fraction" in German language.

$$a_0 + K_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{a_n}$$

In 1898, Alfred Israel Pringsheim gave the following notation for (1) similar to Pietro's notation.

$$a_0 + \frac{b_1}{|a_1|} + \frac{b_2}{|a_2|} + \dots$$

Simple notation for the simple continued fraction (2) is given by $[a_0; a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots]$

1.3 Nice Way to Express Continued Fractions:

Euclidean's Algorithm, a well-known method to express a rational number as continued fraction.

Let us expand the rational number $\frac{61}{13}$

By Euclidean algorithm, $61 = (13)4 + 9$

$$13 = (9)1 + 4$$

$$9 = (4)2 + 1$$

$$4 = (1)4 + 0$$

Hence, we get the below continued fraction expansion for $\frac{61}{13}$,

$$\frac{61}{13} = 4 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{4}}}$$

In short we can write $\frac{61}{13} = [4; 1, 2, 4]$, a finite simple continued fraction.

2. History:

It is hard to pinpoint the origin of continued fraction since it have been studied for over 2000 years. But the bedrock of the continued fraction were formed in late 1600's and early 1700's.

2.1 Time line of Continued Fractions:

Here we have mentioned few important years in which the uses of continued fractions appears.

One of the nice way to express a rational number as continued fraction is using Euclidean algorithm which is the modern version of the algorithm for GCD (greatest common divisor), found in Euclid's Elements (300BCE). After that there is a record that Indian mathematician Aryabhata (550 AD) used continued fraction to solve linear indeterminate equations in Aryabhatiya (499 AD).

Further, Italian mathematician Rafael Bombelli produced continued fraction expansion for $\sqrt{n}$ in particular $\sqrt{13}$ in his book L'Algebra Opera (1572). Following Rafael's work in continued fraction, an Italian mathematician Pietro Antonio Cataldi gave a first notation for continued fraction which plays a major role in development of theory of continued fractions.

After several years an England mathematician John Wallis first introduced the term "Continued Fraction" in his Opera Mathematica (1695). The work of Wallis in continued fraction such as generalizing continued fraction theory and exposing its properties has developed the theory of continued fractions as one of the field in mathematics.

The Dutch mathematician Christiaan Huygens (1629 - 1695) has showed a real life application of continued fraction in his astronomical research. In the period of seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, the theory of continued fraction has evolved gradually.

Leonhard Euler applied continued fraction to prove e is irrational in his work De fractionibus continuis dissertatio (1737). Euler also proved that continued fraction for a rational number is finite and it is infinite for an irrational number in his Introduction in analysi in finitum (1748). In 1761, Johann Heinrich Lambert first proved that π is irrational with the help of continued fraction. Joseph Louis Lagrange (1768) have given a general solution for Pell's equation using the concept of continued fraction.

Furthermore several mathematicians such as Carl Friedrich Gauss (1813), Henri Pade (1892) and Bill Gosper (1972) have contributed their work on continued fraction to flourish the theory of continued fraction.

3. Special Continued Fractions:

In this section we have mentioned several historic continued fractions presented by different mathematicians.

Below mentioned is Rafael Bombelli's continued fraction expansion for $\sqrt{13}$ in 1579,

$$\sqrt{13} = 3 + \frac{4}{6 + \frac{4}{6 + \frac{4}{6 + \dots}}}$$

Followed by Rafael, Pietro Cataldi(1613) gave continued fraction expansion for $\sqrt{18}$,

$$\sqrt{18} = 4 + \frac{2}{8 + \frac{2}{8 + \frac{2}{8 + \dots}}}$$

Euler expressed continued fraction expansion for the general solution of the quadratic equation of the form $x^2 - ax - b = 0$ as follows,

$$x = a + \frac{b}{a + \frac{b}{a + \frac{b}{a + \dots}}}$$

Euler also provided a method to express a infinite series into continued fraction expansion in 1748. For example,

$$e^x = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{x}{1 + x - \frac{2x}{2 + x - \frac{3x}{3 + x - \frac{4x}{4 + x - \dots}}}}}$$

In 1761, Lambert gave the first proof that π is irrational in 1761 from the following continued fraction expansion,

$$\tan x = \frac{x}{1 - \frac{x^2}{3 - \frac{x^2}{5 - \frac{x^2}{7 - \dots}}}}$$

Gauss explicit special continued fraction from hyper geometric functions as given below,

$$\frac{{}_2F_1(a, b + 1; c + 1; z)}{{}_2F_1(a, b; c; z)} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\frac{(a-c)b}{c(c+1)}z}{1 + \frac{(b-c-1)(a+1)}{(c+1)(c+2)}z}}}$$

Following continued fraction is one of the famous expression for π ,

$$\pi = \frac{4}{1 + \frac{1^2}{2 + \frac{3^2}{2 + \frac{5^2}{2 + \dots}}}}$$

Next one is Golden ratio's continued fraction expansion,

$$\varphi = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{1 + \dots}}}}$$

4. Conclusion

Continued fractions have had a major impact on mathematics over the past 2000 years. It gradually became one of the field in mathematics in the 17th century. In this paper we have presented an over view of continued fraction, its brief history and also we have mentioned some historic continued fraction expansions which causes a great impact in the theory of continued fractions.

5. References:

1. A. Dinesh Kumar, R. Sivaraman, Asymptotic Behavior of Limiting Ratios of Generalized Recurrence Relations, Journal of Algebraic Statistics, Vol 13, No. 2, 2022, 11-19
2. R. Sivaraman, J. Suganthi, A. Dinesh Kumar, P. N. Vijayakumar, R. Sengothai, On Solving an Amusing Puzzle, Specialusis Ugdymas, Special Education, Vol 1, No. 43, 2022, 643-647
3. A. Dinesh Kumar, R. Sivaraman, Analysis of Limiting Ratios of Special Sequences, Mathematics and Statistics, Vol 10, No. 4, 2022, 825-832
4. A. Dinesh Kumar, R. Sivaraman, On Some Properties of Fabulous Fraction Tree, Mathematics and Statistics, Vol 10, No. 3, 2022, 477-485
5. M. Vasuki, P. Senthil Kumar, N. Rajesh, On Anti-Q-Fuzzy Deductive Systems of Hilbert Algebras, International Journal of Analysis and Applications, Vol 21, No. 42, 2023, 1-15
6. M. Vasuki, P. Senthil Kumar, Said Broumi, N. Rajesh, On Radical of Neutrosophic Primary Submodule, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol 22, No. 3, 2023 36-52
7. M. Vasuki, R. Sivaraman, Solving Quadratic Diophantine Equation for Integral Powers of 37, International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research, Vol 12, No. 1, 2024, 3996-3998
8. A. Dinesh Kumar, R. Sivaraman, Ramanujan Summation for Pascal's Triangle, Contemporary Mathematics, Vol 5, No. 1, 2024, 817-825
9. P. Senthil Kumar, K. Balasubramanian, A. Dinesh Kumar, Stochastic Model to Estimate the Insulin Secretion Using Normal Distribution, Arya Bhatta Journal of Mathematics and Informatics, Vol 7, No. 2, 2015, 277-282
10. P. Senthil Kumar, A. Dinesh Kumar, M. Vasuki, Stochastic Model to find the Gallbladder Motility in Acromegaly Using Exponential Distribution, International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications, Vol 4, No. 8, 2014, 29-33
11. Sivaraman R, Understanding Ramanujan Summation, International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 2020; 29(7): 1472-1485.
12. Sivaraman R, Sum of Powers of Natural Numbers, AUT Research Journal, 2020; 11(4): 353-359.
13. Sivaraman R, Remembering Ramanujan, Advances in Mathematics: Scientific Journal. 2020; 9(1): 489-506.
14. Sivaraman R, Bernoulli Polynomials and Ramanujan Summation. In: Peng SL, Hao RX, Pal S. (eds.) Proceedings of First International Conference on Mathematical Modeling and Computational

Science. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, Vol 1292. Singapore: Springer; 2021.p.475-484.

15. Sivaraman R, Stirling's Numbers and Polynomials, Bulletin of Mathematics and Statistics Research. 2020; 8(4): 14-19.
16. Sivaraman R, Stirling's Numbers and Harmonic Numbers, Indian Journal of Natural Sciences. 2020; 10(62): 27844-27847.
17. R. Sivaraman, "Exploring Metallic Ratios", Mathematics and Statistics, Vol. 8, No. 4, Pp. 388–391, 2020
18. R. Sivaraman, "Behaviour of Generalized Narayana Sequences", Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, vol. 12, no. 7 – Special Issue, pp. 2558–2564, 2020
19. R. Sivaraman, "Generalized Narayana Sequences and Quadratic Sequences", Advances in Mathematics: Scientific Journal, vol. 9, no. 7, pp. 5143–5149, 2020
20. R. Sivaraman, "Catalan's Triangle and Cayley Numbers", AUT Research Journal, Vol. XI, No. VIII, pp. 8–12, 2020
21. R. Sivaraman, "Generalized Lucas, Fibonacci Sequences and Matrices", Purakala, Vol. 31, No. 18, pp. 509–515, 2020.
22. R. Sivaraman, "Curious Fact about Figurate Numbers", CLIO Journal, Vol. 6, No. 6, Pp. 541–546, 2020.